

Placeholder Name of the conference

Placeholder Session title

© Authors. This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

The Helmholtz Knowledge Graph

towards a FAIR data space within Helmholtz

Volker Hofmann¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2637-0432>,
Gabriel Preuß² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2818-5890>, Lucas
Kulla² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0465-1009>, Stefan Sand-
feld³ <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9560-4728>

¹ Institute for Advances Simulation – Materials Data Science and Informatics (IAS-9), Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Jülich, Germany

² Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Berlin, Germany

³ Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum, Heidelberg, Germany

*Correspondence: Volker Hofmann, v.hofmann@fz-juelich.de

1 Institute for Advances Simulation – Materials Data Science and Informatics (IAS-9), Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH, Jülich, Germany

2 Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Berlin, Germany

3 Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum, Heidelberg, Germany

Abstract

Research in the Helmholtz Association is carried out inter- and multidisciplinary and spans across 18 independently operating research centers across Germany. Within this digital ecosystem, research data and digital assets are heterogeneous in terms of formats, used schemas, record consistency and hosting location. This impairs interoperability and data reuse.

The Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC) is a long term platform supporting convergence in a FAIR data space. As part of this effort we develop Helmholtz Knowledge Graph (Helmholtz KG) [1] as a lightweight interoperability layer and semantic harmonization target, with the aim to connect metadata of Helmholtz digital assets. With the KG, we envision (1) providing better cross-organizational access to Helmholtz's (meta)data and information assets on an upper semantic level, (2) harmonizing and optimizing the related metadata across the association, and (3) forming a basis from which the semantic quality and the depths of metadata descriptions is improved and extended into domain and application levels.

While our KG prototype initially aggregates data provided in schema.org, with our recent works [2] we have established an internal data model that will allow inclusion of data consistent with other semantic standards to standardized semantics (DataCite, Dcat, DC). At the same time we are establishing software for a scalable KG infrastructure, will actively improve the currently

incomplete and inconsistent metadata records through entity resolution and data inference and increase domain specific semantic depth within the various Helmholtz research fields.

Keywords: Knowledge Graph, Helmholtz, Interoperability, Semantics.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: VH, SS together with all other authors; Data Curation: MS, GP, SF, LK; Funding acquisition: VH, SS; Methodology: all authors; Project administration: VH; Resources: VH, SS; Software: MS, GP, SF, LK, FDM; Supervision: VH, SS; Validation: all authors; Visualization: MS, GP, FDM.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests.

Funding

This work was funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), an incubator-platform of the Helmholtz Association within the framework of the Information and Data Science strategic initiative.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledge the OceanInfoHub whose approach inspired and whose codebase supported our development for the Helmholtz KG prototype.

References

- [1] Broeder, J.; Preuss, G.; D'Mello, F.; Fathalla, S.; Hofmann, V.; Sandfeld, S. (2024) The Helmholtz Knowledge Graph: driving the Transition towards a FAIR Data Ecosystem in the Helmholtz Association; The Semantic Web: ESWC 2024, Springer Computer Science Proceedings. doi:[10.34734/FZJ-2024-03156](https://doi.org/10.34734/FZJ-2024-03156)
- [2] Codebase of the Helmholtz KG: <https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/hmc/hmc-public/unhide/development> (Apr. 29th 2025)